

IMPLEMENTING LANGUAGE POLICY AND PLANNING THROUGH MATERIALS DEVELOPMENT PROCESS

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Abstract: This article discusses the implementation process of a language policy and planning by drawing attention to materials development step. It is clearly admitted that planning a new language policy is challenging task that really plays a big role in a language development of a certain country. In order to multiply the effectiveness of the LPP projects, organizers are asked to work harder on developing materials for the project that provides the match between goals and results. Usage of course books whether local or international ones is arguable topic in educational atmosphere.

Keywords: Language policy, language planning, Materials development.

As English has already turned into lingua franca, many countries are working on organizing new LPP (Language policy and planning) projects to improve populations' English literacy. These projects face various problems in implementation process and fail to achieve expected goals due to different reasons, materials development is considered one of the primary aspect in LPP projects which is highlighted in this work. Lack of materials which take into account cultural, economic and political appropriateness to establish a new language policy is considered as a main problem. There are available international course books to use in LPP projects, while many linguists prefer to publish new books for a new language policy.

The purpose of LPP projects is to highlight the improvement of second or foreign languages in a country which includes steps of formulating a language policy, drawing up a plan, and implementing and evaluating LPP project through materials development and use. It is clearly known that LPP is a political process and serves to solve a perceived problem that needs a solution. There may be some situations, which a language policy does not provide the outlined target goals from the project or a language policy and implementation of it does not match with expected results. Additionally, resistance can occur since a language policy may affect a group's identity, their beliefs, their economic conditions and political power. However, these lacks can be mitigated or solved successfully through subsidiarity. Language-in-education planning is described as a beneficial and effective policy which deals with the choice of language on the curriculum and the recruitment and training of educators; the organization and content of the curriculum including assessment; available pedagogic recourses; how materials are going to be taught and how the effectiveness and efficiency of the policy can be measured. In order to increase the effectiveness of LPPs, many approaches are discussed among scholars and language policy makers and all of the approaches have efficiencies and lacks in different contexts. For instance, the adaptive approach is alternative or more possibly effective when decentralization (to have expertise, knowledge and recourses at a lower level to implement a policy) fail due to inadequate recourses. Another approach, a backward mapping is similar to adaptive one but it is bottom-up process that moves from micro to macro level with investigation of the local context and its realities.

Language policy makers use international published books during implementation process of LPPs. It is unreasonable to expect a close match between the chosen international textbooks or course books and the LPP of a country. Many global course books do match the LPP

requirements to use learning English to develop critical thinking and educational development, while a big mismatch is observed in the contents of the global materials and experience and needs of the target learners. National published materials from primary to tertiary levels are preferred to implement in the LPPs. The local publishers are more likely to implement LPP effectively than international materials developers and this statement is proved with the example of Singapore which the national publishers publish three different versions (challenging, normal, easier versions) of their course books for each year of secondary school. However, there may be lacks in the implementation and policy due to mentally and physically separating the process. The most productive method to implementing policy through materials development project is a combination of the forward and backward-mapping. In order to achieve effective LPP implementation, language learning experts should be involved both LPP creating and drafting process to reach compatible results between social, political, educational ideals and language acquisition theory and language learning practice.

The implementation of language planning and policy through materials development is considered one of the most important stage in the development of education in every country. It is difficult to implement any language policy equally throughout the country and it take too much time, even fails sometimes. Troncoso (2010) mentioned that social, cultural, and educational variables of teaching and learning materials should be considered in materials development process. In materials Development, it is known that developing lesson materials according to availabilities of classrooms and learners' needs, wants, lacks is the important requirements of the process. Also, it is important to pay attention to the cultural appropriateness of the content and context of a lesson materials. So, from the beginning of a LPP, people in this process should pay attention every aspect of learning acquisition and do match between target outcomes and materials development. As Kaplan and Baldauf (2007) pointed out that developing materials with experts who are more familiar with local constraints, attitudes and norms influence the implementation of LPP project effectively.

TESL, TEFL and TESOL international programs include special courses called "Language planning and policy" that aims to provide available students or teachers who can select or even participate LPP projects at macro and micro levels. LPP and its implementation is considered one of the challenging educational process and by providing national published materials makes the project more difficult. As Tomalin (2008) mentioned that in ELT classes, material developers should take account of cultural background and skills in that country in which the LPP project has been purposed to implement. In order to achieve satisfactory results in English language usage cultural background can be a bridge appropriate materials developing and LPP project.

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